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D7.1 AI4PublicPolicy Market Platform and AI-based Solutions V1

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CMS	Content Management System
DL	Deep Learning
DSA	Digital Services Act
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FitSM	Federated IT Service Management
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HPC	High Performance Computing
IdP	Identity Provider
IoT	Internet of Things
KEA(s)	Key Exploitable Asset(s)
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
SSO	Single Sign On
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document was developed within the framework of WP7 “Market Platform of AI-based Policy Management Applications and Tools” and describes the work performed in the context of Task 7.1 “Specification, Detailed Design and Implementation of Market Platform” and Task 7.2 “Integration of Validated AI-based Applications and Tools”. The main objectives of these tasks are respectively:

1. To design and implement an on-line market platform as a hosting environment for the project’s results
2. To integrate AI4PublicPolicy solutions for efficient AI-based policy making in the market platform

It presents the design of the AI4PublicPolicy Platform, the technologies identified for its implementation, including the plugins for the interaction of the different technologies, and a complete overview of the platform architecture. A first implementation of the market platform is available at <https://market.ai4publicpolicy.eu/> and in this document the main functionalities are shown.

Moreover, it provides a detailed definition of assets catalogue, and of the provider and asset profile form that is the defined data model to integrate the information into the market platform.

Finally, some recommendations are given on the identification and analysis of the exploitable assets and on the regulation that should be taken into account.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

1.2 Description of WP7

WP7 is responsible for the integration of the project's assets and results in the market platform, and to link and integrate it with the EOSC portal/marketplace. It is also responsible for defining the marketplace branding, designing and delivering a SEO-based, responsive marketplace website and regularly populate and evolve it over the project lifecycle.

The main objectives of WP7 are to:

- (i) design and implement an on-line market platform as a hosting environment for the project's results
- (ii) integrate AI4PublicPolicy solutions for efficient AI-based policy making in the market platform
- (iii) compile and integrate in the market platform training resources and digital transformation assets for public administrations
- (iv) ensure close collaboration and linking with EOSC and stakeholders across the policy management ecosystem, including citizens and businesses

1.3 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this document is to show the available features of the market platform as well as the plan for the next and final version of the market platform.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The first chapter of the document is an introduction to the project and the document.
- The second chapter of the document is the background on the market platform technology that has been deployed for this task.
- The third chapter of the document presents the data model.
- Finally, the document includes a fourth chapter with the conclusions.

1.5 Relation to other WPs and Tasks

The main relation of WP7 with the other WPs are shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

WP7 will interact with all other WPs of the project to integrate all exploitable assets, whereas dedicated tasks in WP7, Task 7.3 and Task 7.4, will integrate the training and digital transformation assets and EOSC services, respectively.

WP2 will drive all the technical development work packages of the project (i.e., WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7) through providing technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture. The main technical components that WP7 will make available on the market platform will be provided by the three core technical WPs, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

WP7 will provide inputs to the co-creation sessions in WP2 and to the pilot operations in WP6, as the training and organisation transformation blueprints of the marketplace will be used in the pilots and in the co-creation.

WP8 will provide the methodology for identifying and analysing the Key Exploitable Assets of the project to be published on the market platform. On the other hand, the market platform will form a key promotional channel for the AI4PublicPolicy results to be exploited in WP8.

2 Specification, Design and Implementation of the Market Platform

The next sections provide a clear view of the created design for the AI4PublicPolicy marketplace, its specification and implementation.

2.1 Marketplace Design

For the design of the Market Platform, two design concepts were created, providing the Consortium the possibility to choose the AI4PublicPolicy marketplace design look & feel.

The main concept for both proposals was people and their needs on governmental policies and how AI growth can respond to such needs. The base colour used for both concepts was inspired by the AI4PublicPolicy original logo (blue and green) finding the perfect balance between them to give both an edgier and modern look to this new platform.

2.1.1 First Concept

For the first concept, the idea was to use a photo with real people, highlighting what aspects they need in their life and the virtual connection of AI to arrange solutions.

For the logo, the baseline was the AI4PublicPolicy existing logo, adding the term “marketplace” to contextualise.

Inspiration mood-board

The concept was inspired by the photo composition shown in Figure 2, representing the connection between the real and the virtual world.

Figure 2. First concept inspiration mood board

The overall result is represented in Figure 3. The zebra crossing was one of the favourite images to develop this concept, and the selected photo was ideal in a way that gives a dynamic look and perfect balance to the design of the AI integrating people’s life.

Figure 3. First concept main image

Logo design

For the logo design, the term “Marketplace” was added to the AI4PublicPolicy logo. The term was coloured based on the main green pattern of the logo, while the font was the same for the sake of uniformity. The term was aligned to the left of logo lines as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. First concept logo design

Homepage Layout

With the dynamicity provided by the main image, the next step was to find the perfect balance between real photos and the colours. Using the available colours, several variations were studied to be used as background colours.

Counters were also one of the points decided to be on the banner area, to provide the user an idea related to the amount of data available on the AI4PublicPolicy marketplace (Figure 5).

Figure 5. First Concept website layout mock-up

2.1.2 Second Concept

A more disruptive design with a vectorial look was devised for the second concept. The AI was the focus of the composition, connecting to a society needs vision. In terms of logo, a fresh new one was designed, based on the AI-cloud link.

Inspiration mood board

The AI connection between knowledge and supplies (machines, smart home, etc) was the inspiration (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Second concept inspiration mood board

The main image (Figure 7) was the result of this creative process. A cleaner look with a simple design where the AI is at the centre of the image and the people are just a reflection of the objective to be achieved by the AI component.

Figure 7. Second concept main image

Logo design

Starting with the project's original logo, a custom logo was designed conveying the concept of machine thinking and robot processes (Figure 8). The colours and fonts from the original logo were used to maintain the consistency through the brand.

Figure 8. Second concept logo design

Homepage Layout

This concept was completely made with vectorial forms and maintains the clean look of the main image.

For the header it uses the same components of the search and counters with a modern look to keep the user focused on the available information (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Second Concept website layout mock-up

2.1.3 Final Concept

After the creation of above two concepts, a doodle poll was circulated among the partners to choose the concept for final development. The voting was balanced between the two options; partners liked the first one as well as some details of the second. Therefore, it was decided, during a follow up meeting of WP7, to produce a third concept which incorporates elements of both the afore-described versions.

The final design has the real people image for the banner and the vector looking for the rest of the website. For the logo, a new one was designed maintaining the project logo and adding the term “Marketplace” beside the main project logo.

Figure 10 represents the main image and the final logo choice.

Figure 10. Final concept

Homepage Layout

In the final option, the elements were merged between the two concepts and gave the branding a clean, balanced and innovative design represented in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Website layout final concept

2.2 Marketplace Specification and Implementation

This section focuses on the specification of the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace, and the identification of the technological base used for its implementation, as well as the delivered results.

2.2.1 Marketplace Specification

Background Technologies

The following paragraphs identify and describe the technologies that support the implementation of a Marketplace and help meeting the identified requirements.

WordPress

WordPress is an open-source Content Management System (CMS) providing several out of the box features enabling non-technical persons the creation and management of web sites. WordPress (as of May 2021) is used by 64.8% of all the CMS based web sites, making it highly supported and maintained.

Its features can be extended by using external plugins or themes. Plugins allow the use of extra features not available on the basic installation such as: advanced user management, contact forms, integration with external applications among others. Using themes gives the user more freedom and choices on how to customise the look of the web site (Figure 12).

WordPress provides a repository with several plugins and themes, some of which provide a free version with basic functionalities requiring a payment to unlock advanced features. WordPress documentation also provides several guides enabling developers to create custom themes and plugins allowing the integration of WordPress with custom-made external applications.

Figure 12. WordPress Admin Menu

WordPress is an open-source project, and its usage is free of charge, however there is a cost if you plan to host your website using the company hosting service which includes different plans according to the requirement of the customer.

IoT-Catalogue.com

The IoT-Catalogue is a web-based tool developed by UNPARALLEL, available at <https://www.iot-catalogue.com> and meant to be the one-stop-source for IoT knowledge, innovations and technologies, aiming to help IoT stakeholders (developers, integrators, advisors, end-users, etc.) to take the most advantage of the Internet of Things for the benefit of society, businesses and individuals. It serves as an explorer for innovations in IoT applications and technologies; that is, a web-based tool that enables to pick & choose IoT solutions; a wide repository of knowledge, use cases, contacts, etc. of the Internet of Things.

A key purpose of the 'IoT Catalogue' is to enable users to explore IoT solutions based on domain-related Value Propositions and/or ICT Problems described on use-cases defined along application domains (Figure 13). The 'IoT Catalogue' also enables users to inspect solutions and technologies from other domains that might fit their intents or analyse use-cases like theirs, thus promoting synergies and reusability between application domains.

Figure 13. IoT-Catalogue overview

The two main functionalities from the IoT-Catalogue used in the Market Platform are the Products and the Use Cases, which are highlighted in the next section.

IoT-Catalogue.com plugin for WordPress

IoT-Catalogue.com provides several customised data subscriptions each one containing a data subset that entails validations and components, a theme and an authorised user (authenticated through a token), IoT-Catalogue.com plugin for WordPress allows the creation of a data subscription with a WordPress instance making available on the Market Platform a list and the detailed pages for each imported component and validation.

The diagram shown in Figure 14 provides a technical overview of data integration between IoT Catalogue and the Market Platform.

Figure 14. IoT-Catalogue.com and Market Platform integration

The diagram gives a technical overview which is organised into three categories, communication between IoT-Catalogue.com and the plugin, internal processes of the plugin including its interactions with WordPress native modules and the communication with the end user.

Training Material Plugin

This plugin adds WordPress support to store and display training/E-Learning resources, it is possible to see a list of all resources which are organised by Workshops and Courses, and detailed information about each resource.

When consulting a Course, it is possible to see a description, duration, cost, certification type, institutions, speakers on the Course and also a website with further information including instructions on how to enrol. The Workshop page shows similar information and includes a YouTube video of the Workshop with a table with all the points discussed in the video as well.

This plugin provides an intuitive interface allowing the user to add new training resources including Workshops and Courses.

2.2.2 Marketplace Architecture

The AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace is based on the WordPress CMS and takes advantage of its Plugin Mechanism to implement most of the functionalities required by the Marketplace and to integrate content available on other sources. Figure 15 depicts the overall architecture of the Marketplace, where the different types of plugins are represented: Functional Plugins, Blocks Plugins and Content Plugins.

Figure 15. Diagram of AI4PublicPolicy Architecture

- **Functional Plugins:** Correspond to the class of plugins that provide specific functionalities to the Marketplace. In the architecture this class is represented by the SSO Login plugin, responsible for enabling Users registered on specific IdPs to login into the Marketplace. Other plugins can also fall under this class but are not represented on the architecture as they provide less relevant functionalities (e.g.: SMTP server configurator, protection against cyberattacks, backups, etc.).
- **Blocks Plugins:** This class of plugins enhance the visual elements available on the WordPress with blocks that communicate with external services and provide specific information or functionalities to the Marketplace. For example, such plugins can be used to integrate functionalities of AI4PublicPolicy components by providing graphical interfaces that expose the interfaces and resources of those components to the users.
- **Content Plugins:** These plugins provide specific facilities to manage specific content on WordPress. While the Blocks Plugins provide visual interfaces to external services, Content Plugins provide a deeper level of integration allowing content to be integrated with WordPress built-in functionalities such as search capabilities, or categories indexing and filtering. Content plugins provide mechanisms for adding and updating new content, either manually by users, or automatically via connection to external services. An example of the latter is the IoT-Catalogue Plugin that collects the information from IoT-Catalogue.com and creates and indexes that content on WordPress. These plugins also provide dedicated visualisation options to compose the pages that present the content to the user. These visualisation options are customised to the content added by those plugins.

2.2.3 Marketplace Implementation

The AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace was implemented to correspond to the concept and specification defined above and can be accessible at <https://market.ai4publicpolicy.eu/>.

Navigation

With the navigation bar, represented in Figure 16, the user can access to Assets and Success Stories pages, search for some data using the search element and access to its account options by clicking on the user icon.

Figure 16. AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace navigation

Homepage

Figure 17 presents the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace website homepage. This homepage is composed of four sections.

Figure 17. AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace website

First, there is a banner with a search element in the middle, and in the bottom some statistics with the total number of Assets and Success Stories available on the website.

Then, a section follows dedicated to the Assets where cards are shown with information about some Assets. The users can get more information about them by clicking on a specific card or if they want to see all Assets they can click on the “See all Assets” button.

Next, there is a section about the Success Stories and, like in the previous section, the user can read some information about some Success Stories. To get more details about them, he/she must click on a specific card or click on “See all Success Stories” to see all Success Stories.

Finally, the footer on the marketplace includes the AI4PublicPolicy logo, contact us and privacy policy links and social media hyperlinks and the necessary EU funding acknowledgement information of the project.

Assets

Figure 18 shows the page dedicated to the Assets available in AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace.

Figure 18. AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace Assets page

In this page, the user can see a list of available assets with their name and respective tags. It is possible to get more information about a specific asset by clicking on the asset name (Figure 19).

Figure 19. AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace Asset detail page

Here, the user can see more detailed information about the selected asset. It is possible to see information related to the categorisation of the asset like type of asset, the trend that it relates to, technical categories where the asset belongs to, or the type of machine learning techniques implemented in the asset. After the section about the categorisation of the asset a new section is shown, that provides detailed information about the asset. In this section is shown a description of the asset and other content that identifies the relations with other assets and the success stories where the asset is already used and validated.

Success Stories

Figure 20 shows the page dedicated to the Success Stories available in AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace.

Figure 20. AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace Success Stories page

In this page, the user can see a list of available success stories with their name and respective tags. It is possible to get more information about a specific asset by clicking in some asset name (Figure 21).

Figure 21. AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace Success Story detail page

Here, the user can see more detailed information about the selected success story. It is possible to see information like description, trend, validation type. In the context of IoT-Catalogue the user can

get the information about the statistics, regions, places, team, value propositions, ICT problems and solutions associated with the success story.

3 Integration of the Project Assets in the Market Platform

Task 7.2 worked to the definition of a service catalogue that, according to the FitSM IT Management standard¹, is a “Customer-facing list of all live services offered along with relevant information about the services”. The initial activity has been to define the structure and format of the service catalogue and create an initial service catalogue. The ongoing activities, that will be reported in the second and final version of this deliverable, will include how to maintain the service catalogue by adding, updating and removing services. FitSM provides selected templates and samples, among which one for the service portfolio and catalogue. The service portfolio is an internal list that details all the services offered, including those in preparation, live and discontinued and may include information such as its value proposition, target customers base, service description, relevant technical specification, cost and price, risk etc. The service catalogue can be regarded as a filtered version of the service portfolio.

One of the ambitions of the AI4PublicPolicy project is to integrate its VPME, datasets, models, AI algorithms, AI tools and other resources, with the EOSC marketplace and, on the other hand, to rely on the EOSC services such as computing and storage resources. To facilitate such integration, the EOSC profiles (metadata schemas describing the EOSC resources) were reviewed, and it was decided to use it by adapting it to the specific needs of the project. In such a way the filled profiles of the assets from the AI4PublicPolicy project will be almost ready to be onboarded in the EOSC marketplace, or even the entire AI4PublicPolicy catalogue could be onboarded as an EOSC catalogue. In fact, even if at the time of our evaluation the version of EOSC Portal Profiles was v3.0, which included two profiles, the Provider Profile and the Resource Profile, now the EOSC profiles have been updated to version v4.0 that, besides a few minor changes to the previous profiles, introduces a new Multi-Provider Catalogue Profile. This version will be evaluated, and the necessary updates applied in the following work of Task 7.2 and reported in the second and final version of this deliverable.

The EOSC onboarding Process requires a Provider to submit information about itself and about the resources it wants to include in the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. The specific information, required or optionally requested, is specified in different “EOSC Profiles”, which are metadata standards for describing Providers and the different kinds of Resources that are supported in the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. The Profiles provide definition of their attributes, their format/type (if any) and multiplicity, as well as whether the attribute is mandatory or optional. The Profiles also include an extensive number of Code lists, Taxonomies, Classifications that have been developed to provide a structured classification of Resources and a harmonised way for the description of various attributes.

Providers are the organisations responsible for “providing” any of the other kinds of resources, and the Provider Profile details the data required to describe each Provider. The AI4PublicPolicy Provider Profile is reported in Appendix 1: Table 4 and is a simplified version of the EOSC Provider Profile² from which some of the optional fields were removed to make the information gathering process easier in the first stage. The list of controlled values describing the Legal Status of the provider is available in the EOSC Provider Profile, and as a selectable list in the spreadsheet that was defined to gather the information from the provider. It’s worth noting that our profile contains all the mandatory information required in the EOSC Provider Profile and so, once filled by a provider, it can be also used to register it in the EOSC marketplace. Appendix 2: Table 6 shows the public fields of the Provider form filled by Reportbrain, one of the project partners and assets provider.

A Resource is an asset made available to perform a process useful to deliver value. Resources include Services, Data Sources, Research Products and any other asset. The AI4PublicPolicy

¹ FitSM IT Service Management standard: <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

² EOSC Provider Profile: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/v3.00+EOSC+Provider+Profile>

Resource Profile is shown in Appendix 1: Table 5 and is based on the EOSC Resource Profile³, where the following categories are maintained:

- Basic Information
- Marketing Information
- Classification Information
- Geographical and Language Information
- Resource Location Information
- Contact Information
- Maturity Information
- Dependencies Information
- Attribution Information
- Management Information
- Access and Order Information
- Financial Information

As for the Provider Profile some optional fields were removed in these categories, to make the information gathering process easier in the first stage, and the classification information category was reviewed completely. In this category it was decided to capture more specific AI related information with respect to the broader and general classification information captured in the EOSC profile.

To this end four mandatory fields were defined: Technical Categories, Research Area, Business Categories, and Type. Moreover, an optional subcategory was included: Machine Learning.

The list of controlled values in the Technical Categories field is the AI subdomain list defined in the “AI Watch. Defining Artificial Intelligence 2.0”⁴ and reported in Table 1.

Table 1. AI Subdomains

Technical Categories	
Knowledge representation	Computer vision
Automated reasoning	Audio processing
Common sense reasoning	Multi-agent systems
Planning and Scheduling	Robotics and Automation
Searching	Connected and Automated vehicles
Optimisation	AI Services
Machine learning	AI Ethics
Natural language processing	Philosophy of AI

The list of controlled values in the Research Areas field is the list of research areas defined in the AI4EU⁵ project for the achievement of a human-centred AI system, which is particularly relevant to this project, that puts citizens at the centre and is based on transparent and trustworthy AI.

These areas are:

- Explainable AI: An AI system should allow humans to understand the reasons behind its recommendations or decisions. It should be possible to know the data, rationale and arguments that lead to a result, to question them and to correct them.
- Verifiable AI: It should be possible to guarantee fundamental properties (e.g., safety, privacy and security) of an AI system both before deployment and at run-time.

³ EOSC Resource Profile: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/v3.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile>

⁴ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC126426>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825619>

- Collaborative AI: An AI system should be capable of operating in collaboration with humans, sharing knowledge with them, and making decisions collaboratively with them. This will lead to AI systems that are safer, more usable, can learn new knowledge, and can adapt to their users.
- Integrative AI: To achieve the above features, AI systems will need to integrate different AI methods and tools into new hybrid techniques, for example, combining data-driven and knowledge-based methods or symbolic and sub-symbolic techniques.
- Physical AI: An AI system should be able to interact with the physical world of humans. To do so, it must go beyond the simplifying assumptions often made in AI, and deal with issues like uncertainty, limited data availability, and limited computational resources.

Further details are available on the research page⁶ of AI4EU project website and in the respective D7.1 “Outcomes from the Strategic Orientation Workshop”⁷. It should be also noted that these are the same research areas identified in the iot.catalogue.com component description.

The list of controlled values in the Business Categories Areas field is the result of the merge of business categories available in the AI4EU asset form and in the IoT catalogue form and is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Business Categories

Business Categories		
Agriculture	Energy	Media
Air Traffic Management	Environment and Sustainability	Public Services
Ambient Intelligence	Fashion	Regional Engagement - DIHs
Art and Music	Finance and Insurance	Retail and e-Commerce
Autonomous Driving and Mobility	Healthcare	Robotics
Citizen Services and Education	Human Resources	Software Engineering
Cloud, Edge and Infrastructure	Industry and Manufacturing	Space
Cultural Heritage	IoT	Telecommunications
Cybersecurity	Law	Transportation
Earth Observation	Maritime Sector	Trust and Privacy

The last mandatory field of the classification information category is the Type, and currently the available options are the same available on the AI4EU asset form and are reported in Table 3.

⁶ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/research>

⁷ Outcomes from the Strategic Orientation Workshop: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5cca7546c&appId=PPGMS>

Table 3. Asset Type

Type
As a Service
Dataset
Docker container
Executable
Jupyter Notebook
Library
ML Model

All other fields that provide a list of controlled value and are not described above, have been taken from the EOSC resource profile and are geographical availability, language availability, resource geographic location, technology readiness, funding body, funding program and order type. They are also available as a selectable list in the spreadsheet defined to gather the information from the resource providers.

3.1 Exploitable Assets Analysis and Identification

This sub-chapter represents the double link between task WP7 “Market Platform of AI-based Policy Management Applications and Tools” and WP8 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization”.

From a preliminary stage, AI4PublicPolicy project shows that it can generate many outcomes, both in terms of numbers and types such as policy development and policy management services, consisting of both AI and non-AI results, including software packages, services, platforms and knowledge bases, as well as methodologies, guidelines, approaches, best practices, lessons learned, etc.

In particular, D8.6 “Business and Exploitation Planning V1” in Chapter 3 specifically in the paragraph 3.1.1 “**Exploitation Planning**” and in 3.1.2 “**Exploitation in AI4PublicPolicy**”, explains in more detail what methodology is used to identify and analyse partners’ and pilots’ assets.

In order to identify which of these results are really exploitable after the end of the project and the correct timing in which they can be exploited, a multi-step methodology was followed.

Specifically, the following steps were deployed:

Phase 1. Sensitisation and envisioning of the AI4PublicPolicy valuable outcomes: Dedicated meetings and workshops were organised to foster common understanding among the project Consortium about the exploitation and partners’ different exploitable results and shared ones, subsequent challenges and suggestions.

Phase 2. Observation and preliminary analysis of the first valuable outcomes: An internal survey examined which outcomes of the project can be exploited internally and externally.

Phase 3. Finalisation of the Key Exploitable Assets List and exploitation routes: The list of KEAs was finalised. The further analysis on the identified KEAs provided an aggregate a table that for each Exploitable Asset the following information is entailed:

- **Name and generic description information**
- **Owners**

- **Intended Exploitation**, this part can also contain information on the target market and on the value proposition.
- **IPRs, patents and license**
- **Documentation/source code**

The list of KEAs, within all information, and methodology followed for identification of asset, extensively discussed in D8.6, will be continuously updated and integrated in the next D8.5 “**Market analysis and business potentials V2**” and in D8.7 “**Business and Exploitation Planning V2**”.

3.2 Legal Aspects

The AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace is designed to be an online market platform which will connect different stakeholders, including citizens, businesses and public sector bodies, and facilitate exchange of information, public policies, and knowledge assets among them. As the service provided in the platform is limited to online hosting service which consists of storing information provided by the recipient of the service, i.e., users, at their request and of dissemination of that information to the public at the request of the users. However, prior to provision of services, it is essential for online service providers to determine the legal basis on which they are willing to provide the services to their users.

For the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace service, a robust set of terms and conditions can serve as a legal ground by establishing a legally binding contract between the users and the platform provider and avoid any misunderstanding about what kind of service the platform provides and on what terms. It is important that the terms and conditions are written specifically for the service. They should not only cover commercial terms such as delivery of assets or property right, but also go a little further than that by limiting the liability of the platform provider, for example, disclaiming the liability for accuracy, quality, safety, legality or lawfulness of the assets offered on the platform, delay in the service caused by force majeure events and protecting the intellectual property rights. In case of a dispute with the users, such terms and conditions may allow the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace to clearly show what it has agreed to provide, what it will not do, what is not allowed on the platform and the limits of its responsibility.

During the discussions concerning the terms and conditions at the meeting with the WP1 leader and the responsible partners, it has been agreed to implement a set of provisional terms and conditions in the platform. However, before launching the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace and thus making the service available to the public, the partners have decided to review and if necessary, to revise these provisional terms and conditions in the follow-up deliverable D7.2 “AI4PublicPolicy Market Platform and AI-based Solutions V2”.

Regarding the EU regulatory landscape, Directive on Electronic Commerce⁸, Digital Services Act⁹ (DSA) and the General Data Protection Regulation¹⁰ (GDPR) are likely to be of direct relevance for the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace. Depending on its business model, for example, whether the provision of hosting service is considered as an economic activity of the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace

⁸ Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce, in the Internal Market ('Directive on electronic commerce'), OJ L 178/1.

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act), OJ L 277/1.

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L 119/1.

provider, its hosting service can be considered as “information society service” as defined in the Directive on Electronic Commerce. Therefore, the service will be subject to the rules set out under the directive on issues such as: i) transparency and information requirements for online service providers; ii) commercial communications; and iii) electronic contracts and limitations of liability of service providers. According to the transparency requirement in Article 5, AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace should provide its users with various information such as (a) the name of the service provider; (b) the geographic address at which the service provider is established; (c) the details of the service provider, including his/her electronic mail address, which allow to be contacted rapidly and communicated within a direct and effective manner; (d) where the service provider is registered in a trade or similar public register, the trade register in which the service provider is entered and his/her registration number, or equivalent means of identification in that register; (e) where the activity is subject to an authorisation scheme, the particulars of the relevant supervisory authority; and (g) tax identification number of the provider if the platform undertakes an activity that is subject to VAT.

Moreover, pursuant to Article 7, without obtaining prior consent from the users, AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace should refrain from sending out unsolicited commercial communication by electronic mails to its users. However, it should be noted that the Directive on Electronic Commerce is an EU directive addressed to the Member States and therefore, the platform provider will be also subject to the national provisions applicable in the Member State(s) where the service provider(s) established on its territory.

In addition, it is noted that further rules concerning the online platforms are introduced under the DSA as complementary to the Directive on Electronic Commerce. Online platform as defined under Article 3(i) also includes providers of hosting services that, at the request of a recipient of the service, store and disseminate information to the public, unless that the dissemination to the public is merely a minor and purely ancillary feature that is intrinsically linked to another service, or a minor functionality of the principal service, and that feature or functionality cannot, for objective and technical reasons, be used without that other or principal service. Considering its role in the AI4PublicPolicy business plan, AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace is likely to be qualified as an online platform under the DSA.

The DSA entered into force on 16 November 2022 and will become applicable as of 17 February 2024 except for the transparency reporting obligations under Article 24(2),(3). According to this article, online platforms are required to publish information on the average monthly active recipients of the service in the EU over the period of the past six months, in a publicly available section of the platform by 17 February 2023 and at least once every six months thereafter. However, given that the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace is not operational at the time of drafting this deliverable, other relevant legal requirements including those explicitly apply to online marketplaces under the DSA will be outlined in the follow-up deliverable D7.2 “AI4PublicPolicy Market Platform and AI-based Solutions V2”.

From privacy and data protection perspectives, it is noted that through the registration forms on the sign-in section and the provider profile forms presented in Appendix-1, the platform will collect personal data such as contact details, addresses, professional titles, names of individuals or their affiliations. The collection of these types of data is likely to constitute processing of personal data by the AI4PublicPolicy Marketplace platform under the GDPR, and therefore the platform needs to comply with various data protection requirements, including but not limited to transparency and lawfulness requirements as explained in the deliverables of WP9 “Ethics requirements”. Furthermore, use of cookies and other tracking technologies in the platform will also trigger the application of consent requirement under the E-Privacy Directive.

At the time of drafting this deliverable, it is noted that the marketplace has a provisional privacy policy in place. Prior to commencing the processing of personal data, the platform will need to obtain

consents from its users through a consent form which will be implemented on the sign-in section. This will further support the platform's compliance with the EU privacy laws.

4 Conclusions and Future Plans

This deliverable is a demonstrator of the first version of the AI4PublicPolicy Market Platform and gives an overview of its design, technologies and implementation whose outcome is already online. Furthermore, it defines the data model, the assets integration and identification process as well as the regulatory landscape to which such platforms are subjected. The work towards the second and final version of this deliverable, due at M33, foresees the integration of all the exploitable assets of the project in the market platform and the continual improvement of such process, including the necessary updates to the data model.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Provider and Resource Profile

Table 4 shows the provider profile form used to gather information about the asset's provider.

Table 4. Provider Profile

Attribute Name	Value	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public
Basic Information						
Name		Full Name of the Provider offering the resource and acting as main contact point.	String (max 100)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Abbreviation		Abbreviation or short name of the Provider.	String (max 30)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Website		Webpage with information about the Provider.	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Legal Entity		A Y/N question to define whether the Provider is a Legal Entity or not.	Boolean	1	Mandatory	Yes
Legal Status		Legal status of the Provider. The legal status is usually noted in the registration act/statutes. For independent legal entities (1) - legal status of the Provider. For embedded providers (2) - legal status of the hosting legal entity. It is also possible to select Not a legal entity.	List of controlled values	1	Optional	Yes
Marketing Information						
Description		The description of the Provider.	String (max 1000)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Logo		Link to the logo/visual identity of the Provider.	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Multimedia		Link to video, slideshow, photos, screenshots with details of the Provider.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Location Information						

Street Name and Number		Street and Number of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Postal Code		Postal code of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	Yes
City		City of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Region		Region of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50)	1	Optional	Yes
Country		Country of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	List of controlled values	1	Mandatory	Yes

Contact Information

Main Contact

First Name		First Name of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	No
Last Name		Last Name of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	No
Email		Email of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	Email	1	Mandatory	No
Phone		Phone of the Provider's main contact person/Provider	String (max 20)	1	Optional	No

		manager.				
Position		Position of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	No
Public Contact						
First Name		First Name of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes
Last Name		Last Name of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes
Email		Email of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general email to contact Provider.	Email	1	Mandatory	Yes
Phone		Phone of the provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general phone to contact Provider.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes
Position		Position of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes

Table 5 shows the resource profile form used to gather information about the assets.

Table 5. Resource Profile

Attribute Name	Value	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public
Basic Information						
Name		Brief and descriptive name of Resource as assigned by the Provider.	String (max 80)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Resource Organisation		The name (or abbreviation) of the organisation that manages or delivers the resource, or that coordinates resource delivery.	String (max 80)	1	Mandatory (automatically filled out from Provider sheet)	Yes
Resource Providers		The name(s) (or abbreviation(s)) of Provider(s)	String (max 80)	Multiple	Optional	Yes

		that manage or deliver the Resource.				
Webpage		Webpage with information about the resource	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Marketing Information						
Description		A high-level description in fairly non-technical terms of a) what the Resource does, functionality it provides and Resources it enables to access, b) the benefit to a user/customer delivered by a Resource; benefits are usually related to alleviating pains (e.g., eliminate undesired outcomes, obstacles or risks) or producing gains (e.g. increased performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving), c) list of customers, communities, users, etc. using the Resource.	String (max 1000)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Tagline		Short catch-phrase for marketing and advertising purposes. It will be usually displayed close to the Resource name and should refer to the main value or purpose of the Resource.	String (max 100)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Logo		Link to the logo/visual identity of the Resource. The logo will be visible at the Portal. If there is no specific logo for the Resource the logo of the Provider may be used.	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Multimedia		Link to video, screenshots or slides showing details of the resource.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Use Cases		Link to use cases supported by this resource.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Classification Information						

Technical Categories		AI technical categories that the AI Resource adheres to.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Research Areas		AI research areas that the AI resource adheres to.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Business categories		Business categories that the AI resource is related to.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Type		Type of resource	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Machine Learning						
Type		Type of Machine Learning: Supervised, Unsupervised, Semi-supervised, Reinforced, Deep, ...	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Technique		Machine Learning Technique(s) used: Classification, Regression, Clustering, ...	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Algorithm		Machine Learning Algorithm: Linear Regression, Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbours, ...	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Application		The model's application from the AI standpoint (Data Processing Machine Learning, Machine Vision Image Processing Robotics, Media and Language Knowledge Extraction, Digital Assistant Chatbots, etc.) and its limitations (e.g., indicate the supported languages for text-related models)	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Architecture		Architecture used: BERT, BiGAN, CNN, DAN, ELMo, etc.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Training Dataset		Dataset(s) used in the model's training: ADE20K, BAIR, HRWSI, ImageNet, etc.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes

Model Format		Format of the model: TF.js, TFLite, Coral, ...	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Fine-tunable		Does the model allow fine-tuning?	List of controlled values	1	Optional	Yes
Geographical and Language Availability Information						
Geographical Availability		Locations where the resource is offered.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Language Availability		Languages of the (user interface of the) resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Resource Location Information						
Resource Geographic Location		List of geographic locations where data, samples, etc. are stored and processed	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Contact Information						
Main Contact						
First Name		First Name of the resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	No
Last Name		Last Name of the resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	No
Email		Email of the resource's main contact person/manager.	Email	1	Mandatory	No
Phone		Telephone of the resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	No
Position		Position of the resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	No
Organisation		The organisation to which the contact is affiliated	String (max 50)	1	Optional	No
Public Contact						
First Name		First Name of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes

Last Name		Last Name of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes
Email		Email of the Resource's contact person or a generic email of the Provider to be displayed at the portal.	Email	1	Mandatory	Yes
Phone		Telephone of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes
Position		Position of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	1	Optional	Yes
Organisation		The organisation to which the contact is affiliated	String (max 50)	1	Optional	Yes
Other Contacts						
Helpdesk Email		The email to ask more information from the Provider about this Resource.	Email	1	Mandatory	Yes
Security Contact Email		The email to contact the Provider for critical security issues about this Resource.	Email	1	Mandatory	No
Maturity Information						
Technology Readiness Level		The Technology Readiness Level of the Resource.	List of controlled values	1	Mandatory	Yes
Standards		List of standards supported by the Resource.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Version		Version of the Resource that is in force.	String (max 10)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Dependency Information						
Required Resources		List of other Resources required to use this Resource.	String (max 50)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Related Resources		List of other Resources that are commonly used with this Resource.	String (max 50)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Related Platforms		List of suites or thematic platforms in which the Resource is engaged or	String (max 50)	Multiple	Optional	Yes

		Providers (Provider groups) contributing to this Resource.				
Attribution Information						
Funding Body		Name of the funding body that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Funding Program		Name of the funding program that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Grant/Project Name		Name of the project that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes
Management Information						
Helpdesk Page		The URL to a webpage to ask more information from the Provider about this Resource.	URL	1	Optional	Yes
User Manual		Link to the Resource user manual and documentation.	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Terms Of Use		Webpage describing the rules, Resource conditions and usage policy which one must agree to abide by in order to use the Resource.	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Privacy Policy		Link to the privacy policy applicable to the Resource.	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Service Level		Webpage with the information about the levels of performance that a Provider is expected to deliver.	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Training Information		Webpage to training information on the Resource.	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Status Monitoring		Webpage with monitoring information about this Resource	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Maintenance		Webpage with information about planned maintenance windows for this Resource	URL	1	Optional	Yes

Access and Order Information						
Order Type		Information on the order type (requires an ordering procedure, or no ordering and if fully open or requires authentication)	List of controlled values	1	Mandatory	Yes
Order		Webpage through which an order for the Resource can be placed	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Financial Information						
Payment Model		Webpage with the supported payment models and restrictions that apply to each of them	URL	1	Optional	Yes
Pricing		Webpage with the information on the price scheme for this Resource in case the customer is charged for.	URL	1	Optional	Yes

Appendix 2: Reportbrain Provider and Resource Profile

Table 6 shows the public and mandatory information of the Reportbrain provider profile form.

Table 6. Reportbrain Provider Profile

Attribute Name	Value	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public
Basic Information						
Name	Reportbrain	Full Name of the Provider offering the resource and acting as main contact point.	String (max 100)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Abbreviation	RB	Abbreviation or short name of the Provider.	String (max 30)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Website	reportbrain.com	Webpage with information about the Provider.	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Legal Entity	Y	A Y/N question to define whether the Provider is a Legal Entity or not.	Boolean	1	Mandatory	Yes
Marketing Information						

Description	Reportbrain provides the most comprehensive knowledge platform, developing software that brings intelligence to every process of your organization. Reportbrain's Artificial Intelligence analyses, monitors, and reports global insights from multiple sources, minimizing the risk in any decision.	The description of the Provider.	String (max 1000)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Logo	https://www.reportbrain.com/rb-press-kit/rb_Vert_RGB-thumb.png	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Provider.	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Location Information						
Street Name and Number	Office 6, 42 Westbourne Grove	Street and Number of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Postal Code	W2 5SH	Postal code of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	Yes
City	London	City of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20)	1	Mandatory	Yes

Country	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK)	Country of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	List of controlled values	1	Mandatory	Yes
Contact Information						
Public Contact						
Email	info@reportbrain.com	Email of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general email to contact Provider.	Email	1	Mandatory	Yes

Table 7 shows the public and mandatory information of the Reportbrain Sentiment Analysis API resource profile form.

Table 7. Reportbrain Twitter Sentiment Analysis API Resource Profile

Attribute Name	Value	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public
Basic Information						
Name	Sentiment Analysis API	Brief and descriptive name of Resource as assigned by the Provider.	String (max 80)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Resource Organisation	Reportbrain	The name (or abbreviation) of the organisation that manages or delivers the resource, or that coordinates resource delivery.	String (max 80)	1	Mandatory (automatically filled out from Provider sheet)	Yes
Webpage	TBD	Webpage with information about the resource	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Marketing Information						

<p>Description</p>	<p>RB Sentiment Analysis API is a powerful tool to extract sentiment and opinion mining from tweets and comments in order to give organizations valuable insights into how the public feels about services or products, topics, world events, and many more. Using complex machine-learning models and customized information flow tools, it goes beyond the simple negative/positive classification of the sentiment, by also detecting the emotion behind the text. RB Sentiment Analysis API is an effective</p>	<p>A high-level description in fairly non-technical terms of a) what the Resource does, functionality it provides and Resources it enables to access, b) the benefit to a user/customer delivered by a Resource; benefits are usually related to alleviating pains (e.g., eliminate undesired outcomes, obstacles or risks) or producing gains (e.g. increased performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving), c) list of customers, communities, users, etc. using the Resource.</p>	<p>String (max 1000)</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>Yes</p>
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	way to discover the sentiment of whole markets, specific segments, or even around persons and organizations.					
Tagline	Public Opinion Mining and Feedback Analysis from Twitter and Comments	Short catch-phrase for marketing and advertising purposes. It will be usually displayed close to the Resource name and should refer to the main value or purpose of the Resource.	String (max 100)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Logo	https://www.reportbrain.com/report-kit/vertical-rgb-thumb.png	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Resource. The logo will be visible at the Portal. If there is no specific logo for the Resource the logo of the Provider may be used.	URL	1	Mandatory	Yes
Classification Information						
Technical Categories	Natural language processing	AI technical categories that the AI Resource adheres to.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Research Areas	Explainable AI	AI research areas that the AI resource adheres to.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Business categories	Cloud, Edge and Infrastructure	Business categories that the AI resource is related to.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Type	As a Service	Type of resource	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes

Geographical and Language Availability Information						
Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)	Locations where the resource is offered.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Language Availability	English (en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese (pt), Bulgarian (bg)	Languages of the (user interface of the) resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes
Contact Information						
Public Contact						
Email	info@reportbrain.com	Email of the Resource's contact person or a generic email of the Provider to be displayed at the portal.	Email	1	Mandatory	Yes
Other Contacts						
Helpdesk Email	info@reportbrain.com	The email to ask more information from the Provider about this Resource.	Email	1	Mandatory	Yes
Maturity Information						
Technology Readiness Level	TRL6 Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)	The Technology Readiness Level of the Resource.	List of controlled values	1	Mandatory	Yes
Version	v1.0	Version of the Resource that is in force.	String (max 10)	1	Mandatory	Yes
Access and Order Information						

Order Type	Request/Order required (Resource requires an ordering procedure)	Information on the order type (requires an ordering procedure, or no ordering and if fully open or requires authentication)	List of controlled values	1	Mandatory	Yes
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